

Mannich Bases from Ethyl 6-Hydroxy-3-methyl-coumarone-2-carboxylate*

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Da Re *et al.*¹ have reported that 3-methyl-7-methoxy-8-dimethylaminomethylflavone hydrochloride (dimeflino) possesses even higher brain-stem stimulating activity than that of picrotoxin. It has a very potent antidotal action in barbiturate poisoning, an intense respiratory analeptic action, and affords a more favourable therapeutic index than any of the other brain-stem stimulants which have come into medical use². Dimeflino on trial on human subjects has been found to exhibit a higher pharmacological activity and lower convulsant dosage than other analeptics³.

TABLE I

No.	R.	Formula.	M.P.**	%Yield.	%Nitrogen.		%Chlorine.	
					Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1.	NMe ₂	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₄ NCl	260°(decomp.)	30	4.58	4.46	11.22	11.32
2.	NEt ₂	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ O ₄ NCl	190°	40	4.21	4.09	10.41	10.39
3.	N-n-Pr ₂	C ₁₉ H ₂₈ O ₄ NCl	178°	38	3.85	3.78	9.72	9.60
4.	N-iso-Bu ₂	C ₂₁ H ₃₂ O ₄ NCl	168°	42	3.40	3.52	8.71	8.93
5.	N-(Isoamyl) ₂	C ₂₃ H ₃₆ O ₄ NCl	262°	30	3.17	3.29	8.20	8.34
6.	N(C ₂ H ₄ OH) ₂	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ O ₆ NCl	164°	62	3.80	3.74	9.41	9.50
7.	N(C ₂ H ₁₀)	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ O ₄ NCl	223°	56	3.85	3.96	10.17	10.04
8.	N(C ₄ H ₈ O)	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ O ₅ NCl	210°	58	3.80	3.93	9.91	9.98
9.	N(C ₄ H ₈)	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ O ₄ NCl	205°	55	4.22	4.12	10.31	10.45
10.		C ₁₈ H ₂₅ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	192°	35	7.63	7.59	9.51	9.63

**All melting points are uncorrected.

* It forms Part V of the series "Oxygen Heterocyclic Compounds as Possible Central Nervous System Stimulants".

1. *Nature*, 1959, 184, 362.
2. Setnikar *et al.*, *J. Med. Pharm. Chem.*, 1961, 3, 471.
3. Gregorio, *Boll. Soc. Ital. Biol. Sper.*, 1960, 36, 521.

Prompted by these observations, we have undertaken a project of synthesising a number of *N*-substituted aminomethyl derivatives from different oxygen heterocyclic systems to screen them for central nervous system-stimulating activity. We have reported earlier⁴⁻⁵ the synthesis of the Mannich base hydrochlorides from 4-methylumbelliferone derivatives.

In the present communication is described the synthesis of the Mannich base hydrochlorides from ethyl 6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarone-2-carboxylate, which has been prepared in good yield by the method of Hantzsch⁶. Mannich bases are prepared in the usual way by refluxing it with paraformaldehyde and different secondary amines, viz., dimethylamine, diethylamine, di-*n*-propylamine, di-isobutylamine, di-isoamylamine, diethanolamine, piperidine, morpholine, pyrrolidine, and *N*-methylpiperazine in anhydrous ethanol. These are isolated as hydrochlorides and are reported in Table I.

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4. Kumar and Joshi, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1963, 26, 149.

5. *Idem*, this *Journal*, 1964, 41, 200, 473.

6. *Ber.*, 1886, 19, 1290.